

GENERATIVE MODELS USING CONTINUOUS VARIABLE QUANTUM COMPUTING

20th June 2022 - 19th Aug 2022

AUTHOR(S)

Jay Patel

Pandit Deendayal Energy University

SUPERVISOR(S)

Sofia Vallecorsa

Michele Grossi

ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo methods have been used to simulate the detectors of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN. But the process of simulating the detectors using Monte Carlo methods is computationally expensive and time-consuming. One of the detectors of LHC, namely the Electromagnetic Calorimeter, which detects the energies of particles, outputs continuous data. In this work, we explore the inherent continuous nature of the Continuous Variable Architecture and try to find out whether or not we can take advantage of that and simulate the detector efficiently using Generative Models with the current Quantum Software and Hardware technologies at our hand. Here, we implement two different models, a Quantum Generative Adversarial Network and a Born Machine in Continuous Variable Architecture, using PennyLane as a Quantum Programming framework and Strawberryfields as a Backend by Xanadu. We analyze the results and determine that the implemented models perform well in learning certain types of probability distributions and not so well for the others. We discuss the reasons for this behaviour of the models and what can be the potential ways to tackle the problem in the future.

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1 INTRODUCTION

We want to explore the continuous variable architecture based generative models and find out whether or not they are useful for our use-case which is to simulate the electromagnetic calorimeter from LHC. But before we take a dive into the models themselves, we need to understand some basics about continuous variable model and How is it different from the qubit model.

1.1 Continuous Variable Architecture

Killoran et al. provides us with the information about CV systems and their physical representation. This section of the report contains parts of that information in order to better understand the CV architecture before using it for our purpose. For a detailed understanding refer to [1].

Many physical quantum systems have inherent continuous nature, light being a prime example of it. Such systems reside in an infinite-dimensional Hilbert space, offering a paradigm for quantum computation which is distinct from the Qubit model. This continuous-variable model takes its name from the fact that the quantum operators underlying the model have continuous spectra.

The CV model is a natural fit for simulating bosonic systems (electromagnetic fields, harmonic oscillators, phonons, Bose-Einstein condensates, or optomechanical resonators) and for settings where continuous quantum operators such as position & momentum – are present. Even in classical computing, recent advances from deep learning have demonstrated the power and flexibility of a continuous picture of computation.

1.1.1 Quadrature Operators

The most elementary CV system is the bosonic harmonic oscillator, defined via the canonical mode operators \hat{a} and \hat{a}^\dagger . These satisfy the well-known commutation relation $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger] = I$. It is also common to work with the **quadrature operators**

$$\hat{x} := \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}}(\hat{a} + \hat{a}^\dagger), \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{p} := -i\sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2}}(\hat{a} - \hat{a}^\dagger) \quad (2)$$

with $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar$. These self-adjoint operators are proportional to the hermitian and anti-hermitian parts of the operator \hat{a} .

We can picture a fixed harmonic oscillator mode (say, within an optical fibre or waveguide on a photonic chip) as a single ‘wire’ in a quantum circuit. These qumodes are the fundamental information-carrying units of CV quantum computers.

By combining multiple qumodes (each with corresponding operators \hat{a}_i and \hat{a}_i^\dagger) and interacting them via sequences of suitable quantum gates, we can implement a general CV quantum computation.

1.1.2 CV States

The dichotomy between Qubit and CV systems is perhaps most evident in the basis expansions of quantum states:

$$\text{Qubit} \quad |\phi\rangle = \phi_0|0\rangle + \phi_1|1\rangle, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Qumode} \quad |\psi\rangle = \int dx \psi(x)|x\rangle \quad (4)$$

For qubits, we use a discrete set of coefficients; for CV systems, we can have a continuum. The states $|x\rangle$ are the eigenstates of the \hat{x} quadrature, $\hat{x}|x\rangle = x|x\rangle$, with $x \in R$.

CV states are generally divided into three types:

- Gaussian States
- Fock States or Number states
- Mixed States

These are then divided into different sub-types, few examples of Gaussian state sub-types would be vacuum states, coherent states, \hat{x} and \hat{p} eigenstates.

1.1.3 CV Gates

Unitary operations can always be associated with a generating Hamiltonian H via the equation

$$U = \exp(-itH) \quad (5)$$

For convenience, we can classify unitaries by the degree of their generating Hamiltonians. We can build an N-mode unitary by applying a sequence of gates from a universal gate set, each which acts only on one or two modes. There are two types of gate in the universal gate set:

- Gaussian Gates
- Non-Gaussian Gates

Gate	Unitary	Symbol
Displacement	$D_i(\alpha) = \exp(\alpha \hat{a}_i^\dagger - \alpha^* \hat{a}_i)$	$\text{---} \boxed{D} \text{---}$
Rotation	$R_i(\phi) = \exp(i\phi \hat{n}_i)$	$\text{---} \boxed{R} \text{---}$
Squeezing	$S_i(z) = \exp(\frac{1}{2}(z^* \hat{a}_i^2 - z \hat{a}_i^{\dagger 2}))$	$\text{---} \boxed{S} \text{---}$
Beamsplitter	$BS_{ij}(\theta, \phi) = \exp(\theta(e^{i\phi} \hat{a}_i \hat{a}_j^\dagger - e^{-i\phi} \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j))$	$\text{---} \boxed{BS} \text{---}$
Cubic phase	$Vi(\gamma) = \exp(i\frac{\gamma}{3\hbar} \hat{x}_i^3)$	$\text{---} \boxed{V} \text{---}$

Table 1: Important CV model gates. Except the cubic phase gate all are Gaussian.

1.1.4 CV Measurements

There are mainly three types of measurements in CV depending upon the measurement operators used for them.

- Homodyne measurements
- Heterodyne measurements
- Photon Counting

Measurement	Measurement Operators	Measurement values
Homodyne	$ x_\phi\rangle\langle x_\phi $	$x \in R$
Heterodyne	$\frac{1}{\pi} \alpha\rangle\langle\alpha $	$\alpha \in C$
Photon Counting	$ n\rangle\langle n $	$n \in N$

Table 2: Key measurement types for the CV model. The Homodyne and Heterodyne measurements are Gaussian, while photon-counting is non-Gaussian.

1.1.5 Qubits to Qumodes

A high-level comparison of CV quantum computation with the Qubit model is depicted in Table 3. In the remainder of this section, we will provide a basic presentation of the key elements of the CV model.

	Qubit Model	CV Model
Basic elements	Qubits	Qumodes
Relevant Operators	Quadrature operators \hat{x} , \hat{p} Mode operators \hat{a} , \hat{a}^\dagger	pauli-operators $\hat{\sigma}_x$, $\hat{\sigma}_y$, $\hat{\sigma}_z$
Common States	Coherent States $ \alpha\rangle$ Squeezed states $ z\rangle$ Number states $ n\rangle$	pauli-eigenstates $ 0/1\rangle$, $ \pm\rangle$, $ \pm i\rangle$
Common Gates	Rotation, Displacement, Squeezing, Beamsplitter, Cubic-Phase	Phase Shift, Hadamard, CNOT, T
Common measurements	Homodyne \hat{x}_ϕ , Hetero- dyne $Q(\alpha)$, Photon- Counting $ n\rangle\langle n $	Pauli-basis measurements $ 0/1\rangle\langle 0/1 $, $ \pm\rangle\langle\pm $, $ \pm i\rangle\langle\pm i $

Table 3: Comparison between Qubit and CV model.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Aim: Define and implement generative models in CV architecture to take advantage of its inherent continuous nature to simulate the continuous outputs of the Electromagnetic Calorimeter of the LHC and analyse the advantages and disadvantages of the model.

In the field of high energy physics, energy distribution data of a particle is of high important. Even though this can be experimentally measured, there is potential use of simulated data whether it be for prediction future collisions in LHC or for testing physics model. Generally, Monte Carlo simulations are used simulate and generate this data because of their high accuracy but they are computationally expensive and time consuming. To solve this problem many generative models have been introduced with their pros and cons. In this work we explore the pros and cons two CV based generative models and analyse if they possess any advantage for our task with the current technologies at use.

Before we start defining our models let's take a look at What Calorimeter is?, How does the data we are trying to simulate looks? and Why do we want to use CV for it?

2.1 Calorimeter

In our context, Calorimeter is one of the detectors from CERN's LHC experiments which measures the energy of the particle. They are designed to absorb most of the particles coming from a collision, forcing them to deposit all of their energy and stop within the detector. ATLAS calorimeters consist of layers of an "absorbing" high-density material that stops incoming particles, interleaved with layers of an "active" medium that measures their energy. Electromagnetic calorimeters measure the energy of electrons and photons as they interact with matter. Hadronic calorimeters sample the energy of hadrons (particles that contain quarks, such as protons and neutrons) as they interact with atomic nuclei. Calorimeters can stop most known particles except muons and neutrinos.[2]

Figure 1: Computer Generated image of the ATLAS calorimeter [3]

2.2 Dataset Analysis

Our dataset contains the output of electromagnetic calorimeter. It outputs 3-Dimensional energy distributions of deposited energies on every pixel during the event of a particle detection. Calorimeter has 3-D pixel arrangement of shape (51,51,25) respectively on each axis. Hence the output data of each event contains has same shape.

But for simplicity we reduce the dimensionality of our data to 1-D by collapsing the first two axis on the last one. We have data of 10000 such events hence the shape of our dataset is (10000, 25).

2.2.1 Event Wise Analysis

Figure 2: Event-wise energy distribution histogram of 25 pixels

From the plot we can observe the errors and the mean value. Even though, at a particular event all the pixels seems to follow a Gaussian-like (not Gaussian) distribution, keeping in mind the deviation of every pixel it seems as if each pixel follows a distribution. It's too early to say that we can create a model which can learn this distribution.

To say any further we will have to analyse the data pixel-wise and check whether or not the deviation we see in Figure 2 are random experimental errors (noise) or it actually follows a distribution.

2.2.2 Pixel Wise Analysis

Below image shows the pixel-wise energy distribution of all 10000 events. Top-left being the 1st pixel and bottom-right being the 25th.

Figure 3: Pixel-wise energy distribution histogram of 10000 events

From the plots we can confirm that the deviation we saw in Figure 2 comes from the standard deviation of data following a distribution.

A point to notice here is that the distribution for each pixel is different and most of them are non-Gaussian. But this conveys that no matter the event, if the particle is same, the energy value will follow a certain distribution and if we can learn these distribution we can simulate the calorimeter data.

2.3 Why use CV?

2.3.1 Drawbacks of Qubit Model

We can create a model using Qubit model that can generate data from Figure 2. In that, we will assign each Qubit to represent a pixel and learn the corresponding values. The limitation of the qubit model lies here, as the model can learn a value per Qubit (in this case the mean value) but not a distribution. Hence it will generate data but it won't follow the pixel-wise distribution we observed in Figure 3. But if we were to make the model follow a distribution then, we will have to discretise the pixel-wise data of 10000 events and compress it so that a handful number Qubits can learn a distribution of a single pixel and we do the same for each pixel. This method has a drawback that, we will need a large number of Qubits and it still is not efficient because we have 10000 events per pixel and compression of this data will lead to errors in simulation.

2.3.2 Potential Benefits of CV Model

If we use CV model, we know that each Qumode is a continuous physical system and when measured the sample values follow a probability distribution. Hence, if we use a model that can transform that probability distribution into the a desired one, we can assign a Qumode for each pixel. But the complexity of a Qumode is higher than that of a Qubit so we will first try to simulate a smaller system in which data is compressed to 3 pixels. Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows what we want to achieve.

Figure 4: Pixel-wise energy distribution histogram of 10000 events for 3 pixels

Figure 5: Event-wise energy distribution histogram of 3 pixels

3 MODEL ARCHITECTURE

Now that we have seen what CV is and what our data looks like, we can use this information to train CV based models for learning the energy distributions of our training dataset. For this purpose we use two different CV based generative models listed as below:

1. Continuous Variable Quantum Generative Adversarial Network (CVQGAN)
2. Continuous Variable Born Machine (CVBM)

3.1 Continuous Variable Quantum Generative Adversarial Network

Ever since their first introduction Generative Adversarial Networks [4] are being used for learning and generating samples from probability distributions. In HEP, simulating energy distributions is of high importance and classical GAN models like CaloGAN [5] have shown promising results in terms of accuracy and time complexity compared to Monte Carlo methods. Recent advances in the field of quantum machine learning has lead to the introduction of quantum GAN (qGAN) [6] and their potential use for learning and generating probability distributions over discrete variables [7].

Implementation of qGAN for 1D and 2D probability distributions of the electromagnetic calorimeter outputs has shown convincing results. But as we know the output data of the calorimeter is continuous and above models use discretisation on that data and then perform the reconstruction. Using CV model to generate probability distributions over a continuous variable might just be a solution for this problem. A recent approach do that for simulating electromagnetic calorimeter outputs with hybrid GAN [8] has shown promising results. Hybrid GAN model has a Quantum Generator and a Classical Discriminator, In this work we will try to implement a fully quantum GAN in CV model.

3.1.1 Architecture

Figure 6 shows the architecture and the training method of the CVQGAN model that we have used.

Figure 6: Architecture and training illustration of CVQGAN model

3.1.2 Training

We have Quantum Neural Networks at play defined by parameterized variational quantum circuits i.e. $U_g(\theta_g)$ for Generator and $U_d(\theta_d)$ for Discriminator, where U_g and U_d are Unitary functions representing Generator and Discriminator respectively and θ_g and θ_d are training parameter (weights) for U_g and U_d respectively.

First we embed the noise into Generator circuit using Amplitude Embedding. Then we train the discriminator over real inputs from our training data and fake inputs generated by the Generator. We use a sigmoid activation function and calculate the loss using binary cross entropy function.

Here generator loss and discriminator loss are defined as suggested in the original introduction of GAN [4].

$$DiscriminatorLoss = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [\log D(x^{(i)}) + \log(1 - D(G(z^{(i)})))] \quad (6)$$

$$GeneratorLoss = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \log(1 - D(G(z^{(i)}))) \quad (7)$$

where, $x^{(i)}$ and $z^{(i)}$ are samples from real data and noise respectively and m is the number of samples.

Using these loss values we update the Discriminator and Generator parameters and continue this process until a certain number of epochs or convergence. Once trained, we can use Generator to produce the samples from required probability distribution. here each Qumode used represents a pixel of calorimeter from the Figure 4 and 5.

3.2 Continuous Variable Born Machine

Born machine is a pure quantum model which can produce a probability distribution over a discrete variable using Born's Measurement rule (Equation 8) which signifies the fundamental randomness of the quantum mechanics and this model is referred as Quantum Circuit Born Machine (QCBM) [9].

Because of Born Machine's fully quantum nature there is no classical counterpart of this model hence it is a perfect example of quantum advantage against classical computing methods. Since its first introduction there have been other studies which have demonstrated QCBM's use for generative probabilistic modelling [10, 11].

A recent study on the use of Born Machine for Ising Hamiltonians shows that the results of this model seems to outperform the previous standard methods [12]. similar to our goal a study on Monte Carlo event generation using Quantum Circuit Born Machine has shown convincing results [13]. But again they discretise the data to train the model to learn to generate probability distributions over a discrete variable.

A recent study uses continuous variable quantum computing to solve the discretisation problem and further enhance previously derived models [14]. The model we will implement is based this study but we use it to simulate the data from the output of the electromagnetic calorimeter.

3.2.1 Architecture

Figure 7 shows the architecture and the training method of the CVBM model that we have used.

Figure 7: Architecture and training illustration of CVBM model

3.2.2 Training

We first define our variational quantum circuit $U(\theta)$ where U is the Unitary function representing the circuit and the θ is the representation of the circuit parameters. The key part here is the measurement, Born Machine follows Born's measurement rule showed in the Equation 8.

$$P(x) = |\langle x|\psi(\theta)\rangle|^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where, } |\psi(\theta)\rangle = U(\theta)|0\rangle^{\otimes n} \quad (9)$$

According to Born's measurement rule we calculate the probability distribution of a continuous random variable (in our case not in the original definition) by simultaneously measuring all the Qumodes of the variational quantum circuit and taking the expectation value of that measurement.

With this we calculate the loss using the MMD (Maximum Mean Discrepancy) Loss Function. It uses a kernel to calculate the distance between the target and the predicted probability distributions. For this task other other loss functions like KL Divergence and Sinkhorn Divergence might be applicable as well because the need is to accurately calculate the distance between the target and the predicted distributions.

In the case of MMD we need a kernel that can easily map the predicted data into the shape of the target data. Formula for a Gaussian kernel is shown in the Equation 10.

$$k_G(x, y) = e^{\left(\frac{-c\|x-y\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} \quad (10)$$

4 TEST RESULTS AND FUTURE WORK

The implementation of both the models was done using python. We used a quantum machine learning library PennyLane [15] for implementation of variational circuit and the training procedure. We used integration of Strawberryfields [1] Photonic Quantum Simulator Backend with PennyLane for simulating our circuits. For both the models the variational circuits have been created using the layers referred from Killoran et al. [1]. For Generator and Discriminator circuits in CVQGAN we use multiple combinations of layer-depth for testing and the best results so far are shown in the Figure 8 with generator depth of 5 layers and discriminator depth of 3 layers. For the variational circuit in the CVBM we used the final depth of 3 layers and the results are shown in the Figure 9.

Figure 8: Energy values for all 3 pixels using CVQGAN

Figure 9: Energy values for all 3 pixels using CVBM

4.1 Result Analysis and Conclusion

If we look at the results shown in the Figure 8 and 9 we can say that both the models show high accuracy in learning the probability distribution of 3^{rd} pixel and not so much for the others. A reason behind this could be because of the distribution followed by 3^{rd} pixel. If we look at the Figure 4, we can see that the 3^{rd} pixel seems to follow a near Gaussian distribution. Fundamentally the CV vacuum states are Gaussian in nature and hence transforming them into another Gaussian state or probability distribution is relatively simple.

On the other hand, Non-Gaussian states are superposition of infinite Fock states. Same goes for the Non-Gaussian transforms like Kerr or Cubic phase transforms. On a quantum computer (photonic) this is fundamental but if we try to simulate them on a simulator running on a classical computer, it will need to store and compute operations on an infinite dimensional matrix which is simply not possible. To solve this we use so called Fock Truncation where we truncate the number of dimensions required for the matrix to work. efficiently it's a trade-off between complexity and accuracy but in this case low number of Fock dimensions seems to not work properly and large number of it takes too many resources. Hence we conclude that until these computations can be performed on a real photonic quantum computer with noise tolerance we will face problems simulating Non-Gaussian probability distributions.

4.2 Future Work

One of the possible solution might the use of quantum computers could be to use NISQ (Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum) Devices [16] in photonic architecture with highly accurate error-correcting codes. One of the reason for the slow development of new models in CV is because of its high time complexity. With each new Qumode the complexity of the model increases exponentially which keeps our options limited. To solve this we normally use JAX integration of PennyLane to access GPU usage and vectorisation functionality. But many functions of this integration seems to not work well with Strawberryfields backend yet as it is under development. This issue can be tackled first in the future. In the case of CVBM, while using MMD loss function Gaussian kernel seems to have work really well for producing Gaussian distributions but for Non-Gaussian distribution we can find a better kernel function that changes with parameter and can be tuned using parameter tuning for each distribution. Entirely other loss functions can also be tested.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Author wants relay his thanks to his supervisors Sofia Vallecorsa and Michele Grossi for their support during the entire programme and their guidance and information about the project. Author shares his gratitude towards Su Yeon Chang for information, discussion and access to the code for her work on Continuous Variable Hybrid GAN [8], Ieva Čepaitė for information and access to the code for her work on Continuous Variable Born Machine [14], Alexandru Mihai Hau for the discussion about 3D GAN implementation for Monte Carlo simulations, Saverio Monaco for the suggestions on PennyLane's intergration of JAX and Samuel Simko for the discussion about kernel functions. This project was a part of Openlab Summer Student Programme at CERN and Author thanks to the whole Openlab Team as well as CERN for this amazing opportunity and his fellow Summer Students for a fabulous summer.

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